

EcoPlastic

Eco conversion of lower grade PET and mixed recalcitrant PET plastic waste into high performing biopolymers.

D6.2 PROJECT WEBSITE AND SOCIAL MEDIA ACCOUNTS

Call: HORIZON-EIC-2021-PATHFINDEROPEN-01

Type of Action: HORIZON-EIC

Grant Agreement n°: **101046758**

Project acronym: **EcoPlastiC**

Project name: **Eco conversion of lower grade PET and mixed recalcitrant PET plastic waste into high performing biopolymers**

Start Date/Duration: 1st October 2022 / 36 Months

Deliverable n° & Title: **D6.2 Project website and social media accounts**

Due date: 30th November 2022

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Version	Date	Author	Organisation	Description
1	10/01/2023	Gordana Minovska	IMGGE	First draft
2	18/01/2023	Jelena Lazic	IMGGE	Second draft
3	20/01/2023	Jasmina Nikodinovic-Runic	IMGGE	Third draft
4	25/01/2023	Margaret Brenan	TUS	Final version

Type of document (Dissemination Level)	
Public	x
Sensitive	
EU Classified	

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European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe EIC Pathfinder programme under grant agreement No 101046758.

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Abbreviation list

DEC – Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication

DMT – Data Management Plan

IMGGE – Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic Engineering

KTH – KTH Royal Institute of Technology

NOVA – NOVA School of Science and Technology | FCT NOVA

TUS – Technological University of the Shannon: Midlands Midwest

WP – work package

GA – grant agreement

EIC - European Innovation Council

EC – European Commission

EU – European Union

Executive Summary

Deliverable 6.2 is a report on the EcoPlastiC Project Website and is one of the most powerful dissemination tools for reaching the largest audience possible, including groups beyond the scientific community and the project's stakeholders.

The main objectives of the project website are:

- **Present** the project's scope, details, goals, mission, and vision.
- **Communicate** project progress, activities, and results.

The guiding principle for the website is to **embody & convey the project ethos** emphasising EcoPlastiC as a technological leap for low carbon plastics. The EcoPlastiC Project aims to deliver the science of a future technology that has the potential to change the paradigm of how we deal with unrecyclable mixed plastic waste. The project's website follows this ambition to be bold and radically different and present a technological innovation in its domain.

To achieve excellence, we pay close attention to both the quantitative (performance, accessibility, best practices, SEO) and the qualitative (website organization, visual design content quality) aspects of websites.

The brand has been designed to provide a strong visual identity connecting with people on the projects mission to convert plastic waste to sustainable bio-polymers. This distinctive brand design reinforces the position, promise and ethos of the project and advocates its key values to achieve routes to circularity for plastics.

This document elaborates on all the aspects of the project website.

1. Project website

1.1. Introduction

Since EcoPlastiC is a Horizon Europe project, it is **hosted on a .eu domain**.

The EcoPlastiC Website can be found at the following URL: <https://ecoplasticproject.eu/>

This domain has been purchased for the entire duration of the project (36 months). The initial version of the website was active within two months of the project's start. However, being a vital extension and communication interface of the project, the website will continue to be developed, modified, and updated in parallel with the project for the entire project lifecycle.

1.2. Features

Top-notch performance

Unlike the vast majority of similar websites that are built with website builders, or slow and outdated platforms such as WordPress, the EcoPlastiC project website is custom-made using cutting-edge web technology that provides superb speed, performance, and user experience (UX).

Speed and performance are an afterthought for many websites. We claim that it is **the foundation** of everything else. If a website is so slow that users just leave even before it loads, it truly does not matter how well-designed it is, or how relevant the content is. It is like failing an exam by not showing up for it. Except, we don't even know that we failed because we don't know how many visitors we lose because of the poor performance of the website. There is no tool that can measure how many users tried, but did not visit our site.

This is well understood in the web tech world, and there are quantitative metrics that indicate the quality of a website. Web Vitals is an initiative by Google to provide unified guidance for quality signals that are essential to delivering a great user experience on the web. More information on this topic can be found [here](#).

We continually measure and improve the [core web vitals](#) important for website performance, accessibility, best practices, and SEO (Search engine optimization). We use the Lighthouse Chrome plugin as a quantitative website quality tool and generate a report on each major version release. We take great pride in the stellar performance of the EcoPlastiC website and hope that it will set a new, higher standard for science-related websites.

[Lighthouse report 9 Jan 2023.pdf](#) (Annex 1)

Light/Dark mode

A unique feature of the EcoPlastiC website is the ability to switch between a light and a dark mode. In addition to being delightful, this feature improves the accessibility of the website and opens it to a range of users who might have medical reasons for their website color theme preferences.

Beautiful & modern visual design

The website is designed to feel clean, modern, and unpretentiously futuristic, with subtle associations to the aesthetics of plastic. It uses **modern web animations** that accentuate the messages delivered through the content, without compromising the speed and performance of the website. The animations, along with the **attractive hover effects** create visual interest and increase the visitor's engagement with the content. As a special touch, our website features custom, **expertly designed icons** that complement the short textual description of each process.

Expertly crafted information architecture

We understand that people don't read websites from top to bottom like we read books or scientific papers. We all come to the web with extremely short attention spans and just skim the content, looking for either something that catches our interest or a pertinent piece of information. Our website makes it easy for the user to find both.

The content on the website is crafted with the best UX (User experience) practices in mind. It has an intuitive website organization (information architecture), without the clutter of deeply nested menus and jargon terms that might be confusing to the general audience.

The content is meticulously tailored for the web. It is kept brief and interesting, yet relevant, accurate, and informative.

Privacy-Friendly Analytics

Measuring website outreach and visits necessitates collecting data. The most widely used tool for this purpose is Google Analytics. Despite its complexity and the fact that it is making websites slower, it is the dominant solution simply because it is free. However, free only means we don't pay money for it, but we pay with our privacy. Google Analytics works by using tracking cookies - small pieces of code that get stored in the user's computer and send data on the user's web activity.

Nowadays there are laws that regulate and protect users' privacy. Website users have to be informed how their data is collected, used, and shared, and have to give their explicit or implicit consent. That is why we often see banners informing us that a website uses cookies, and we get to accept or reject them.

EcoPlastiC website is committed to protecting our users' privacy. We do not use cookies, and that is why we do not need that annoying cookie banner on our website. We use Plausible Analytics that collects data using an entirely different, privacy-friendly approach.

Our Analytics stats are available at this link:

<https://plausible.io/share/ecoplasticproject.eu?auth=OUQlrlwsoGlabkqFKYnyp>

SEO & Social media sharing optimizations

The EcoPlastiC website implements all the technical aspects important for Search Engine Optimization. Additionally, we have added the appropriate markup (Open Graph meta tags) in order to have an eye-catching & impactful presentation when the content of our website is shared on social media.

Snapshots created using [Open Graph Debugger/ Simulator | RAKKOTOOLS](#)

1.3. Structure and organization

Header & Footer sections

The website header and footer are sections present on every page and remain the same across the entire website.

The header is the topmost section of the website. It remains fixed at the top on scrolling the page. Thus, it is always easily accessible for the user. It contains (from left to right):

- EcoPlastiC Project logo
- Main navigation links
- Social media links
- Dark/Light theme switch

The navigation link of the currently active page is distinct from the others.

The footer is the bottommost section of the website. It contains:

- EU funding acknowledgments
- Secondary navigation links (legal pages)
- Copyright disclaimer
- Disclaimer mandated by the Grant Agreement (17.3)

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1.4. Pages

Home page

The initial page of the website is the homepage. The homepage has the following sections:

1. **Hero section** - the first section of the homepage that highlights the main information about the project. It has a link to the About page, where the user can read about the project in more detail.

2. **Partners section** - the logos of the partners along with a brief description and a link to the Partners page. Each of the logos, when clicked leads to that partner's section on the Partners page.

PARTNERS

We have diverse and complementary backgrounds in material science, polymer engineering, enzymology, microbiology, bioengineering and chemical engineering.

[READ MORE](#)

3. **Mission section** - provides a high-level overview of the main project mission. Currently, this section has an animation that serves as a temporary placeholder for the future project video that has not been produced yet. Once the video is ready, it will replace the current animation

In the later stages of the project, we intend to add another section to the homepage that will highlight the latest news about the project.

About page

The about page provides more information about our project. The text is easy to read and understand, and the animations add visual interest.

It has the following sections:

1. Challenge section

CHALLENGE

Linear approach to plastics is a losing game

Only 1.2% of all the plastic ever produced has been recycled and is still in use. Most of the recycled plastic bottles are turned into clothing, and are recycled **only once** before they end up in a landfill.

95% of the value of plastic packaging material, worth **USD 80-120 billion annually**, is forever lost to the economy, while adding to global greenhouse gas emissions.

Mixed plastic is our biggest challenge. Such plastic is deemed unrecyclable, due to complex issues of materials separation, and the inferior purity and grade quality of the recycle.

2. Project vision section

VISION

Putting mixed PET plastics into a perpetual bio-cyclable loop

The technology developed in this project will lead to the production of research-grade PHA biopolymers, which can be regenerated perpetually and used in the same or similar applications as the equivalent fossil fuel produced virgin polymer, thereby reducing the carbon footprint.

Our long-term goal is for the process to be applicable to virtually any plastic material such multilayer packaging (including PET, PE, PP and barrier layers such as EVOH, PA, metallized films) but also flexible films that cannot be recycled cost effectively to date

3. Project approach section

OUR APPROACH

Degradation

Series of mechano-green, chemical and biocatalytic technologies

Biofiltration

Novel process for the preparation of highly fermentable monomer and oligomer feedstock streams

Biopolymerization

Microbiome processing to produce new biopolymers from monomer feedstocks

PHA Recovery

Green recovery including optimized enzyme cocktail will be employed

Validation

Enhancing biopolymer properties & creating demonstration prototypes

4. Project impact section

IMPACT

Far-reaching effects of the next-generation bioplastics

This technology has the potential to completely transform the plastics industry - drastically reducing the amount of virgin material produced from petroleum extraction, and positioning recycled PET as a valuable & reusable resource.

In addition to engineering, our project is relevant to several SPIRE sectors derived from chemicals and plastics which are characterized by a high dependence on fossil raw materials and energy in their production and processing technologies and are therefore under greater pressure to shift to circular models.

Our projects aligns with the UN Sustainable Development Goal on Sustainable Consumption and Production (SDG12) and the EU Climate Plan. Moreover, being the technological lead for next generation plastics creates key intellectual property (IP) and new jobs in industrial manufacturing of bioplastics in Europe.

5. **Project details** - at the end of the page are the factual details of the project, as well as a link to the project's CORDIS profile.

<p>Project title</p> <p>Eco conversion of lower grade PET and mixed recalcitrant PET plastic waste into high performing biopolymers</p> <p>Go to CORDIS profile</p>	<p>Duration</p> <p>3 years</p> <p>from 1 Oct 2022</p>	<p>EU Contribution</p> <p>+3 M</p> <p>(EUR)</p>	<p>Partners</p> <p>5</p> <p>5 EU countries</p>
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Partners page

Each partner is presented within a partner section that follows the same structure (from left to right):

TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY OF THE SHANNON: MIDLANDS MIDWEST

Moylish Park Campus
V94 EC5T Limerick
Ireland

Project Management **Green Depolymerization**

As the project's coordinator, TUS focuses on all aspects of project management, progress reporting and EU Communication.

In addition, building on proprietary high-throughput PET and polyester depolymerization technologies, further mechano-green chemical processes will be developed and tailored for efficient PET monomer and other polymer monomer production from mixed PET plastics.

TEAM LEADER

Dr. Margaret Brennan-Fournet
PRISM Assistant Director

- Institution information - logo, name, address, country. The logo and the institution's name are links to their website.
- Text about the partner's role in the project. At the top, labels designate the respective work packages.
- Team leader image, name, and title. The image and name are links to the researcher's profile (ORCID or LinkedIn).

News page

The news page is where we'll post about the project's activities and events. It starts as the smallest, but as the project matures, this page going to be the most dynamic and largest part of the website. Currently, the website has its first post:

Each post has a cover image, a category label, a title, a date, introductory text, and a link to the full post. Once clicked, the link opens the full post:

Meeting

First general assembly at AIMPLAS

January 5, 2023

Today's technology enables us to work remotely and collaborate internationally towards solving challenges and creating a better future together. Our EcoPlastiC project team is one where partners from five different countries join forces towards delivering the science behind a new technology of plastics. We rely heavily on remote means of communication and collaboration in our day to day work. However, we recognize the importance of meeting each other in person, networking and discussing our project.

Therefore, we are thrilled to announce our first general assembly meeting on **25 January 2023**, which will take place at **AIMPLAS**, a technology centre with 30 years of experience in the plastics industry.

During this one-day event, each of the partners will present their work package (WP):

- WP1 - Project Management (TUS)
- WP2 - Green Depolymerisation & mixed PET waste Plastics (TUS)
- WP3 - Design and Optimisation of the AVE Microbiomes (AVECOM)
- WP4 - Recovery of PHA (NOVA)
- WP5 - Processing and packaging prototype (KTH)
- WP6 - Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication (IMGGE)

The presentations will be followed by an open discussion and a summary of priority actions by the Project Coordinator (TUS).

As an added benefit of AIMPLAS as a venue for this event, we look forward to get acquainted with their multiple **R & D projects** pertinent to the field of circular plastics economy.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe EIC Pathfinder programme under grant agreement No 101046758

The project leading to this application has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe EIC Pathfinder programme under agreement No 101046758

LEGAL

[Terms of use](#)
[Privacy policy](#)

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Downloads page

The downloads page contains all relevant downloadable materials. The user interface contains a filter that facilitates finding the desired category of documents. Besides communication kit documents, this page will contain publications, newsletter issues, reports, etc.

DOWNLOADS

Downloadable documents

Our repository for presentation and communication materials, newsletters, publications and press releases

All categories ▾	NAME	DESCRIPTION
Communication kit	Brochure	EcoPlastiC project promotional brochure
Communication kit	Roll-up	Three variants of EcoPlastiC project roll-up
Communication kit	Logo	Project logo and slogan

Contact page

The contact page has a contact form with reCaptcha (I am not a robot) spam protection. In addition, it exposes a direct contact email of the lead beneficiary institution - IMGGE.

CONTACT

Get in touch

If our work resonates with you and you have further questions, comments or you seek collaboration with us, we would love to hear from you.

Name

Email

Message

I'm not a robot

reCAPTCHA
Privacy • Terms

SEND MESSAGE

By submitting this form you confirm that you agree to our terms of service and privacy policy.

INSTITUTE OF MOLECULAR GENETICS AND
GENETIC ENGINEERING

Vojvode Stepe 444a
11042 Belgrade

Serbia

✉ info@ecoplasticproject.eu

2. Social media accounts

All social media that were included in the Grant Agreement have been created.

2.1. Twitter

EcoPlastiC project @_EcoPlastiC_ [https://twitter.com/ EcoPlastiC](https://twitter.com/EcoPlastiC)

TweetDeck will be used for scheduling posts.

2.2. LinkedIn

Company page: EcoPlastiC <https://www.linkedin.com/company/ecoplastic-project/>

Post will be scheduled.

2.3. Facebook

Page: Ecoplastic <https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100088412644481>

Post will be scheduled.

2.4. Instagram

EcoPlastiC project @ecoplastic_project https://www.instagram.com/ecoplastic_project/

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for monitoring

- **Reach** (umbrella term for how many people come across our social media accounts and posts): follower count
- **Impressions** (how many times a post or profile has been seen)
- **Post reach** (the number of unique accounts that saw the post)
- **Web traffic** (how well posts with links to the website are performing): someone clicked from the social media account to get to one of our website pages
- **Social media engagement** - clicks, likes, shares, comments, mentions, profile visits

Setting SMART goals

Specific: Our goals should be clear, simple, and defined.

Measurable: This is where analytics come in (KPIs). We want a goal that has one or more metrics.

Achievable: Is it achievable or is it not possible within our resources?

Realistic: With our current resources of time and money, is it possible to achieve our goals?

Time-sensitive: Every goal needs a time frame, whether it's one year or several months.

Annex 1 – Lighthouse report (09/01/2023)

https://ecoplasticproject.eu/

Performance

Values are estimated and may vary. The [performance score is calculated](#) directly from these metrics. [See calculator.](#)

▲ 0–49 50–89 90–100

METRICS

[Expand view](#)

First Contentful Paint
1.1 s

Time to Interactive
4.2 s

Speed Index
1.7 s

Total Blocking Time
100 ms

Largest Contentful Paint
1.4 s

Cumulative Layout Shift
0

[View Original Trace](#)

[View Treemap](#)

Show audits relevant to: All FCP TBT LCP CLS

OPPORTUNITIES

Opportunity

Estimated Savings

These suggestions can help your page load faster. They don't [directly affect](#) the Performance score.

DIAGNOSTICS

Minimize main-thread work — 3.7 s \, \,

User Timing marks and measures — 4 user timings \, \,

Keep request counts low and transfer sizes small — 59 requests • 401 KiB \, \,

Largest Contentful Paint element — 1 element found \, \,

Avoid long main-thread tasks — 8 long tasks found \, \,

Avoid non-composited animations — 10 animated elements found \, \,

More information about the performance of your application. These numbers don't [directly affect](#) the Performance score.

PASSED AUDITS (33)

Show

97

Accessibility

These checks highlight opportunities to [improve the accessibility of your web app](#). Only a subset of accessibility issues can be automatically detected so manual testing is also encouraged.

CONTRAST

Background and foreground colors do not have a sufficient contrast ratio. \, \,

These are opportunities to improve the legibility of your content.

ADDITIONAL ITEMS TO MANUALLY CHECK (10)

Show

These items address areas which an automated testing tool cannot cover. Learn more in our guide on [conducting an accessibility review](#).

PASSED AUDITS (18)

Show

NOT APPLICABLE (25)

Show

100

Best Practices

TRUST AND SAFETY

- Ensure CSP is effective against XSS attacks

↕

GENERAL

- Detected JavaScript libraries

↕

PASSED AUDITS (13)

Show

NOT APPLICABLE (1)

Show

92

SEO

These checks ensure that your page is following basic search engine optimization advice. There are many additional factors Lighthouse does not score here that may affect your search ranking, including performance on [Core Web Vitals](#). [Learn more](#).

CONTENT BEST PRACTICES

- Links do not have descriptive text — 2 links found

↕

Format your HTML in a way that enables crawlers to better understand your app's content.

ADDITIONAL ITEMS TO MANUALLY CHECK (1)

Show

Run these additional validators on your site to check additional SEO best practices.

PASSED AUDITS (11)

Show

NOT APPLICABLE (2)

Show

Captured at Jan 9, 2023, 5:21
PM PST
Initial page load

Emulated Moto G4 with
Lighthouse 9.6.6
Slow 4G throttling

Single page load
Using Chromium 108.0.0.0 with
devtools

